

Flexibility Justice in Electrified Heating: Governing Domestic Thermal Energy Storage to Avoid Widening Inequality

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Abstract

Electrifying domestic heat is central to net zero, but it reconfigures affordability and security: thermal comfort and hot-water services become increasingly coupled to electricity prices, network constraints, and flexibility market design. Domestic thermal energy storage (TES)—via hot-water cylinders, compact thermal stores, and building thermal mass in heat-pump-led systems—can provide low-carbon heat flexibility, reduce peak coincidence, and support renewable integration. However, storage-enabled flexibility is not distribution-neutral. Evidence from demand-response governance, distributional tariff analysis, and storage adoption patterns indicates that unequal access to enabling assets and unequal capacity to shift demand can produce regressive outcomes, where vulnerable households bear disproportionate burdens in cost, risk, or reduced energy service.

This paper develops a justice-aware, non-simulation screening and targeting framework for storage-enabled flexibility in electrified heating. Justice is operationalised using distributional, recognition, and procedural tenets, defining regressive outcomes as net effects that increase inequality through disproportionate burdens on vulnerable groups. The framework integrates: (i) Energy Performance Certificate (EPC)-derived dwelling and system attributes; (ii) area-level vulnerability profiling (income proxies, deprivation metrics, tenure prevalence); and (iii) literature-calibrated TES feasibility bounds. Outputs are three normalised indices (0–1): TES Readiness (physical/integration feasibility), Justice Feasibility (participation barriers), and Exposure (risk under price variability when flexibility is constrained). Indices are aggregated to postcode-level scores and typologies to support targeting, sequencing, and safeguard design. Robustness *will be assessed* via weight/threshold sensitivity and construct-validity checks to support technical credibility without dispatch optimisation.

Keywords

heat electrification, flexibility governance, energy justice, fuel poverty

1 Introduction

Electrifying domestic heat is central to net zero, but it reconfigures affordability and security: thermal comfort becomes increasingly coupled to electricity prices, network constraints, and flexibility market design. In this setting, domestic thermal energy storage (TES)—via domestic hot-water (DHW) cylinders, buffer/compact thermal stores, and building thermal mass in heat-pump-led systems—constitutes a major distributed storage

layer in the demand sector [4, 15, 18, 22]. TES can provide low-carbon heat flexibility by decoupling heat generation from heat use, thereby reducing peak coincidence and supporting renewable integration [4, 15]. Practical implementation studies further show that heat flexibility can be delivered through structured control options and third-party control of heat pumps, while documenting real-world constraints such as overrides and comfort considerations [7, 20].

However, storage-enabled flexibility is not distribution-neutral. Demand-response and flexibility governance research highlights uneven consumer outcomes and ethical risks where programmes assume universal capacity to shift demand or ignore constraints on energy service [3]. Empirical evidence on the energy flexibility divide and the broader “flexibility gap” shows that enabling assets and flexibility opportunities are socio-spatially uneven and can interact with deprivation outcomes [14, 16]. Distributional analyses of time-of-use (ToU) tariffs demonstrate heterogeneous impacts across socio-demographic groups, implying regressive effects where access to flexibility is unequal [21]. Adoption evidence from residential storage diffusion similarly indicates that uptake and subsidy allocations can concentrate in higher-income areas [2]. UK evidence on flexibility participation and acceptance indicates that engagement depends on everyday routines and on cost, context and convenience, while broader critiques of automated demand management emphasise the importance of transparency, consent, and legitimacy conditions [1, 12, 13]. Building-energy research also shows that buildings can constrain what occupants can realistically do, reinforcing that deliverable flexibility is bounded by building and household constraints rather than choice alone [8, 10].

This motivates an explicitly justice-aware storage framing. We adopt established energy justice tenets—distributional, recognition and procedural—to define *regressive outcomes* as net effects that increase inequality through disproportionate burdens (cost, risk, or reduced energy service) borne by vulnerable groups [9, 17]. Deliberative evidence on UK systems flexibility governance further highlights vulnerability, compensation and empowerment as salient fairness expectations for flexibility transitions [19]. More broadly, clean energy transition research emphasises that equity outcomes are shaped by policy design and by how benefits and burdens are distributed [6], including in low-carbon infrastructure transitions linked to energy poverty alleviation objectives [11]. Evidence on domestic demand response adoption further suggests that programme and market design influence uptake and outcomes, reinforcing the importance of governance choices in flexibility delivery [5].

This paper addresses the research question: *Under what dwelling, socio-economic, and governance conditions can domestic TES support heat decarbonisation without widening inequality?* We contribute a justice-aware, non-simulation screening and targeting framework for TES-enabled flexibility in electrified heating. Rather than claiming dispatch-optimised schedules or precise

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kW/kWh savings under specific tariffs, the method produces decision-ready diagnostics by separating: **TES Readiness**, **Justice Feasibility**, and **Exposure**, aggregated to postcode-level scores and typologies with robustness checks.

2 Related Work

This section positions the contribution at the intersection of (i) domestic TES and building thermal flexibility in electrified heating, (ii) demand-side response and tariff-driven flexibility with heterogeneous household impacts, and (iii) energy-justice and governance perspectives that motivate safeguards against regressive outcomes. The review is organised to clarify what is already established technically, what is known about distributional risk and participation constraints, and where the gap remains for scalable decision-support that links feasibility, access barriers, and exposure risk in one framework.

2.1 TES and heat electrification as a storage-enabled flexibility pathway

Domestic TES and building thermal mass are established sources of short-duration flexibility in electrified heating [4, 15]. Work quantifying flexibility from residential thermal mass demonstrates how flexibility services depend on building characteristics and comfort constraints [4]. Reviews of domestic TES applications emphasise design parameters and deployment considerations that shape whether TES contributes meaningfully to flexibility services [15]. Review literature on heat pump–TES coupled systems further synthesises configurations and modelling approaches, including integration of heat pumps with thermal storage media such as phase-change materials [18, 22]. Implementation evidence indicates that residential heat flexibility can be delivered through defined control options and third-party control approaches, while documenting practical constraints such as comfort preferences and override behaviour [7, 20].

2.2 Pricing, demand response, and heterogeneous household impacts

Distributional analyses of time-of-use tariffs show heterogeneous impacts across household types and time-use patterns, implying that tariff reforms can advantage or disadvantage socio-demographic groups [21]. Demand-response governance research highlights ethical risks and uneven outcomes where programmes assume universal shifting capacity or treat essential energy services as fully discretionary [3]. UK programme evidence shows that demand flexibility participation is embedded in everyday routines and shaped by enabling technologies and household circumstances [12]. Social acceptance research similarly finds that participation depends on cost, context, and convenience [13]. In parallel, critiques of automated demand management argue that scalable automation requires social licence conditions such as transparency, trust, and perceived fairness [1]. Evidence on domestic demand response adoption further underscores the role of programme design and market arrangements in enabling participation and shaping outcomes [5].

2.3 Flexibility divide, inequality mechanisms, and justice frameworks

Empirical evidence on the energy flexibility divide demonstrates that enabling assets and flexibility opportunities are socio-spatially

uneven and can interact with deprivation outcomes [16]. Complementary analysis of a broader “flexibility gap” similarly points to socio-economic and geographic drivers of unequal flexibility [14]. Adoption evidence from residential storage diffusion indicates that storage uptake and subsidy allocations can concentrate in higher-income communities, motivating explicit attention to how benefits and burdens are distributed [2]. Energy justice frameworks provide conceptual grounding for operationalising these concerns, distinguishing distributional, recognition, and procedural justice [9, 17]. UK deliberative evidence on systems flexibility governance highlights vulnerability, compensation and empowerment as salient fairness expectations [19]. These perspectives align with broader clean energy transition research showing that equity outcomes are shaped by policy design and by how burdens and benefits are allocated [6], including in low-carbon infrastructure transitions linked to energy poverty alleviation [11].

2.4 Constraints, deliverable flexibility, and decision-support needs

A recurring theme across the flexibility literature is the gap between technical potential and what can be safely delivered under real constraints. Building flexibility scholarship emphasises that flexibility is multi-dimensional and context-dependent, raising questions about which metrics matter, for whom, and under what constraints [10]. Research on occupant behavioural freedom highlights that buildings can constrain what occupants can realistically do, and that some buildings allow only limited behavioural intervention [8]. Together, these insights motivate decision-support methods that separate technical plausibility from participation feasibility and risk, particularly for essential heat and hot-water services.

2.5 Gap addressed by this paper

Most TES–heat pump research focuses on technical performance and modelling, while Demand Side Response (DSR) justice and distributional work often addresses inequity mechanisms without operationalising housing feasibility constraints at scale. This paper bridges the two by proposing a reproducible, non-simulation screening method that links EPC-observable feasibility constraints to participation barriers and exposure risk, generating postcode-level decision surfaces and governance pathway implications for equitable TES-enabled flexibility deployment.

3 Methodology

This section specifies the proposed screening framework as a transparent mapping from available evidence to decision-ready outputs. We first define the input data architecture (EPC-derived dwelling/system attributes and area-level vulnerability proxies), then formalise the three bounded indices—TES Readiness (R), Justice Feasibility (F), and Exposure (X)—and their aggregation to postcode-level scores. Finally, we describe how indices are translated into a priority typology and governance pathways, and outline robustness checks that evaluate stability of rankings and classifications under alternative plausible assumptions.

3.1 Overview and design principles

We develop a justice-aware, *non-simulation* screening and targeting framework for storage-enabled flexibility in electrified heating. The goal is not to produce dispatch-optimised schedules

or precise kW/kWh savings under specific tariffs, but to generate *decision-ready diagnostics* that indicate: (i) where domestic TES is technically plausible; (ii) where participation barriers are likely to constrain access; and (iii) where tariff-driven or market-mediated flexibility could create risk of adverse outcomes. This design responds to evidence that demand response outcomes can be uneven and ethically problematic when programmes assume universal capacity to shift demand [3], and to evidence that flexibility opportunities and enabling assets are socio-spatially uneven [14, 16]. It also reflects building flexibility scholarship emphasising that flexibility is multi-dimensional and bounded by constraints rather than purely by preference [8, 10].

3.2 Inputs and data architecture

The framework integrates three input blocks:

- (1) **EPC-derived dwelling and system attributes.** From Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs), we extract observable indicators: EPC band/rating, floor area, age band, and descriptive fields for heating and hot-water systems. These fields provide scalable evidence of thermal performance and system characteristics relevant to TES integration.
- (2) **Area-level socio-economic vulnerability profiling.** We attach area-level indicators including income proxies, deprivation metrics, and tenure prevalence to represent socio-economic vulnerability and participation barriers that are not fully captured by building descriptors.
- (3) **Literature-calibrated TES feasibility bounds.** We use the domestic TES and building thermal flexibility literature to define plausibility constraints and bounded shifting potential, rather than claiming dispatch optimisation [4, 15, 18, 22]. Field and implementation evidence on heat pump flexibility motivates explicit consideration of controllability and user constraints [7, 20].

3.3 Operationalising justice: indices and definitions

We operationalise justice using distributional, recognition, and procedural tenets [9, 17]. We define *regressive outcomes* as net effects that increase inequality through disproportionate burdens (cost, risk, or reduced energy service) borne by vulnerable groups. This aligns with deliberative evidence on fairness expectations in UK flexibility governance, including vulnerability, compensation and empowerment [19], and with work emphasising that equity outcomes in clean transitions depend on policy design [6, 11].

We produce three normalised indices for each dwelling i :

$$R_i, F_i, X_i \in [0, 1], \quad (1)$$

where R_i is TES Readiness (technical plausibility), F_i is Justice Feasibility (participation accessibility), and X_i is Exposure (risk under price variability with constrained flexibility).

3.3.1 Index 1: TES Readiness (R_i). TES Readiness captures whether TES-enabled heat flexibility is *plausible* given EPC-observable constraints. It is a screening score (not a performance model) that aggregates bounded sub-indicators:

$$R_i = \sum_{k=1}^K w_k x_{ik}, \quad \sum_{k=1}^K w_k = 1, \quad x_{ik} \in [0, 1]. \quad (2)$$

Default weights w are set transparently to emphasise storage presence and integration plausibility, consistent with TES parameter sensitivity discussions in the literature [15, 22]. Readiness

is interpreted as: high values indicate plausible TES integration; low values indicate TES-first strategies are likely constrained and may require retrofit/controls sequencing.

Missingness handling and data quality. EPC fields can be missing or ambiguous. For a base run, missing sub-indicators are assigned a neutral value (e.g., $x_{ik} = 0.5$) and a data-quality count q_i is recorded:

$$q_i = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbb{1}[x_{ik} \text{ missing}]. \quad (3)$$

We then bound uncertainty via missingness sensitivity (Section 3.6), avoiding over-confidence in low-evidence areas.

3.3.2 Index 2: Justice Feasibility (F_i). Justice Feasibility represents whether households can realistically participate in TES-enabled flexibility without disproportionate procedural/recognition burdens. Operationally, F_i is constructed from area-level proxies for:

- **Tenure constraints** (e.g., renting prevalence, limited ability to approve upgrades),
- **Capital constraints** (e.g., income proxies, limited credit),
- **Administrative burden** (e.g., proxy variables indicating barriers to programme uptake).

This index directly responds to evidence that flexibility opportunities and enabling assets are unevenly distributed [14, 16] and that participation is shaped by routines and acceptance conditions, not solely by price incentives [1, 12, 13]. Higher F_i indicates fewer barriers to fair participation; lower F_i indicates that enablement and safeguards are more likely to be necessary.

3.3.3 Index 3: Exposure (X_i). Exposure captures the risk of adverse outcomes under price variability when flexibility is constrained. It is designed to represent where tariff-driven flexibility could translate into bill distress or overheating risk when households cannot shift safely. The motivation is supported by distributional evidence on ToU tariffs [21], DSR governance risks [3], and the concept that building constraints limit behavioural freedom [8]. Operationally, X_i combines (i) energy-burden vulnerability proxies and (ii) dwelling thermal sensitivity proxies (e.g., EPC band).

3.4 Aggregation to postcode-level scores

For mapping and programme design, we aggregate dwelling-level indices to postcode p :

$$R_p = \frac{1}{n_p} \sum_{i \in p} R_i, \quad F_p = \frac{1}{n_p} \sum_{i \in p} F_i, \quad X_p = \frac{1}{n_p} \sum_{i \in p} X_i, \quad (4)$$

where n_p is the number of EPC records in postcode p . We report n_p alongside scores to flag low-evidence postcodes.

3.5 From indices to decision support

The indices are combined into a decision support pipeline as shown in Figure 1.

3.5.1 Priority typology. We define “high” and “low” relative to thresholds T_R and T_X applied to postcode scores (e.g., $T_R = \text{median}(\{R_p\})$ and $T_X = \text{median}(\{X_p\})$), yielding four typology classes. Sensitivity to alternative thresholds (e.g., quartiles) will be assessed as part of robustness testing (Section 3.6). We translate postcode scores into a simple 2×2 priority typology based on Readiness (R_p) and Exposure (X_p), producing four categories:

Figure 1: Decision support pipeline: postcode-level indices (Readiness, Feasibility, Exposure) are aggregated into priority typologies and interpreted through governance pathways (S1 market-led uptake, S2 targeted enablement, S3 fairness-conditioned participation).

- **Fair market:** high R_p and low X_p (market-led uptake more defensible with standard protections),
- **Targeted enablement + protections:** high R_p and high X_p (TES plausible but inequality risk high),
- **Protection-first:** low R_p and high X_p (retrofit/controls sequencing and safeguards dominate),
- **Lower priority:** low R_p and low X_p (TES is less feasible and exposure is low, subject to local objectives).

Justice Feasibility (F_p) is treated as a modifier/gate: low F_p flags that targeted enablement (S2) and/or fairness-conditioned participation (S3) is more likely required even when R_p is high, because participation may otherwise be excluded or disproportionately burdensome. Justice Feasibility (F_p) is treated as a modifier/gate that strengthens the need for enablement and fairness-conditioned participation where barriers are high.

3.5.2 Governance pathways. Consistent with UK deliberative evidence on fairness expectations [19] and broader equity implications of clean transitions [6, 11], we interpret typology classes through three governance pathways:

- **S1 Market-led uptake:** benefits concentrate where readiness and feasibility are already high.
- **S2 Targeted enablement:** bundle TES with support where exposure is high and readiness is feasible.
- **S3 Fairness-conditioned participation:** specify safeguards (minimum service guarantees, opt-out, transparency, benefit-sharing) to prevent harm to constrained households [1].

3.6 Robustness and construct validity

To support technical credibility without dispatch optimisation, we will assess:

- **Weight sensitivity:** we will vary w for R_i and measure rank stability (e.g., Spearman correlation of postcode ranks).
- **Threshold sensitivity:** we will vary typology thresholds (median vs quartiles) and measure class stability.
- **Missingness bounds:** we will re-run the scoring with missing sub-indicators set to 0 and 1 to bound uncertainty.
- **Construct validity:** we will test expected monotonic relationships (e.g., higher X_p with higher deprivation; lower F_p with higher barriers), consistent with distributional risk mechanisms in tariff and flexibility literature [16, 21].

4 Results: planned outputs and demonstration artefacts

This proceedings paper reports decision-ready artefacts defined by the proposed screening framework, rather than dispatch-optimised operational results. The primary outputs are: (i) postcode-level index maps for TES Readiness (R_p), Justice Feasibility (F_p), and Exposure (X_p); (ii) a postcode typology and priority surface that translates index combinations into governance-relevant classes; and (iii) pathway-aligned recommendations indicating where market-led uptake is defensible and where targeted enablement and safeguards are required. These outputs are intended to support early-stage programme design, targeting, and sequencing under the constraints that deliverable flexibility is bounded by building characteristics and household constraints rather than universal shifting capacity.

4.1 From indices to governance-relevant decisions

Figure 1 summarises how postcode-level index scores are translated into priority typologies and then interpreted through governance pathways, making the framework outputs directly usable

for targeting and safeguards design. In brief, the typology uses TES Readiness (R_p) and Exposure (X_p) as the primary decision axes, while Justice Feasibility (F_p) acts as a modifier/gate that increases the need for enablement and protections where participation barriers are high. This structure operationalises the paper’s central claim: storage-enabled flexibility can create regressive outcomes when access to enabling assets and capacity to participate are uneven, so governance design must be contingent on both technical plausibility and risk.

4.2 Illustrative inequality signal: readiness gradients across socio-economic context

To illustrate the type of distributive pattern the framework is designed to detect, Figure 2 shows an example readiness gradient across postcode deciles ordered by an income proxy (low→high). If TES Readiness increases with socio-economic advantage, then market-led uptake (S1) risks concentrating benefits where capability is already high, while high-exposure areas may require targeted enablement and protections. In the full application, the same diagnostic is produced using empirical postcode-level scores and reported alongside sample sizes (n_p) and uncertainty flags.

Figure 2: Illustrative TES Readiness distribution across postcode deciles ordered by an income proxy (low→high). If readiness increases with advantage, market-led uptake can concentrate benefits unless enablement and safeguards are targeted.

5 Discussion: governance implications for equitable TES-enabled flexibility

This section interprets the screening outputs as governance-relevant evidence rather than as operational performance results. Building on the postcode-level indices and typology in Section 4, we explain how different combinations of TES Readiness, Justice Feasibility, and Exposure imply different policy responsibilities: where market-led uptake may be acceptable, where targeted enablement is needed to avoid exclusion, and where protections must be prioritised to prevent regressive outcomes. In doing so, the discussion translates the decision artefacts (Figures 1–3) into practical pathway logic for programme design.

5.1 Interpreting typologies as governance choices (S1–S3)

The typology does not prescribe a single “best” policy; it indicates where particular governance pathways are likely to be defensible or risky. In this framing, R_p is the technical feasibility signal, X_p is the harm-risk signal, and F_p is the access/barrier signal; governance is the mechanism that aligns these signals with do-no-harm delivery. Building on the interpretation above (where R_p is the technical feasibility signal, X_p is the harm-risk signal, and F_p is the access/barrier signal), we summarise the governance pathways as:

- **S1 Market-led uptake (high R_p , low X_p):** Where Readiness is high and Exposure is low, market-led uptake may be defensible, subject to baseline consumer protections.
- **S2 Targeted enablement + protections (high R_p , high X_p):** Where Readiness is high but Exposure is also high, TES may be technically plausible yet socially risky; targeted enablement plus protections becomes the appropriate framing, because relying on tariffs and voluntary participation alone can concentrate benefits among already-advantaged households.
- **S3 Fairness-conditioned participation (guardrails; especially when X_p is high and/or F_p is low):** Across contexts, fairness-conditioned participation provides minimum safeguards to prevent harm to constrained households (e.g., minimum service guarantees, opt-out rights, transparency, and benefit-sharing). In the high-exposure, low-readiness case, this implies a protection-first stance: TES should not be treated as the immediate solution, and retrofit/controls sequencing and safeguards should precede any expectation of tariff response.

5.2 From typology to policy instruments

Figure 3 translates the typology into policy levers and illustrative UK instruments. The central design principle is do-no-harm: if flexibility is expected from households, programmes must also provide protections and targeted enablement where capability is low. Practically, this implies bundling TES with controls and, where needed, fabric upgrades; designing tariffs and incentives that do not penalise low-flex households; and ensuring that flexibility value is shared fairly and transparently. In UK settings, this logic maps to area-based delivery routes, bill protections (e.g., rebates/social tariff-style options), landlord pathways and minimum standards, and flexibility procurement rules that embed consumer protections as conditions of participation.

5.3 Limitations and next steps

This is a screening and decision-support method: it does not model dispatch-optimised heat-pump–TES operation, quantify peak kW reduction, or estimate bill impacts under specific tariffs. Instead, it identifies where TES-enabled flexibility is technically plausible, where participation barriers are likely to constrain uptake, and where exposure risk is high—providing a defensible basis for targeting enablement and specifying safeguards. In addition, Justice Feasibility and parts of Exposure are operationalised using area-level proxies (e.g., tenure prevalence and income/deprivation indicators), which can mask within-area heterogeneity; we therefore treat postcode classifications as decision-support signals and flag low-evidence areas rather than household-level determinations. A natural next step is to layer techno-economic and operational modelling (and, where

Figure 3: Translation from typology to policy: generic policy levers and illustrative UK instruments for targeted enablement and protections in TES-enabled flexibility roll-outs.

possible, measurement) within the priority areas identified by Figures 1 and 3, to quantify system value and household impacts under candidate tariff and procurement designs.

6 Conclusion

Domestic TES can provide low-carbon flexibility by shifting heat and hot-water demand away from peaks. However, storage-enabled flexibility is not distribution-neutral: unequal access to enabling assets, unequal capacity to participate, and heterogeneous exposure to price variability can produce regressive outcomes where vulnerable households bear disproportionate burdens.

This paper contributes a justice-aware, non-simulation screening and targeting framework that operationalises these concerns by separating feasibility, access, and risk into three distinct decision signals—TES Readiness, Justice Feasibility, and Exposure—aggregated to postcode-level scores and typologies and interpreted through governance pathways (S1 market-led uptake, S2 targeted enablement, S3 fairness-conditioned participation). The outputs are decision-ready artefacts (Figures 1–3) that support targeting, sequencing, and safeguard design without requiring dispatch optimisation at this stage.

The central implication is that TES should be treated as equity-sensitive infrastructure: where readiness is high but exposure and barriers are also high, enablement and protections must be bundled; where exposure is high and readiness is low, protection-first and retrofit/controls sequencing should precede flexibility expectations. Future work will quantify operational and distributional impacts by layering techno-economic modelling and measurement onto the priority areas identified by the screening outputs. Overall, if a programme requires flexibility from households, it must also provide targeted enablement and do-no-harm protections where capability is low, so participation does not widen inequality.

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